

PENZANI, Renata. **A coisa brutamontes** [The thug thing]. Illustrations Renato Alarcão. Recife: Cepe, 2018.

REVIEW¹

Maria das Graças Monteiro Castro²

The book tells the story of Cicero, an eleven-year-old boy who has to cope with the death of a loved one. Grounded on a child's perception of death, the narrative addresses grief and sadness in a light-hearted way. The book was shortlisted for the Prêmio Barco a Vapor award in 2016 and won the Prêmio Cepe Nacional de Literatura Infantojuvenil in 2017. Book illustrations are by illustrator, designer, and professor of Visual Arts Renato Alarcão.

Keywords: Death. Sadness. Grief.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2019 Bologna. Books published in 2018 and reviewed in 2019. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

² Voter.